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ON THE INDEPENDENCE OF THE BOARD AND ITS COMMITTEES, AND EARNINGS QUALITY

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ABSTRACT

This study revisits the effects of the board and its committees' independence on earnings quality. We contribute to the board-earnings quality by using a balanced panel of 154 publicly listed firms corporate-level data for 15 years (2008-2022) to conduct our analysis and by accounting for endogeneity using a Generalised Method of Moments approach when assessing the association between the board and its committees' independence and earnings quality. We find that board independence, audit committee independence, risk committee independence, and firm size are statistically significant. We find no statistical significance in nomination committee independence, remuneration committee independence, profitability, listing age, and leverage and earnings quality. These findings provide empirical evidence for the board and its committees' independence, and earnings quality literature.

Keywords: audit committee independence, board independence, earnings quality, firm size, leverage, listing age, nomination committee independence, profitability, remuneration committee independence, risk committee independence

JEL Classification Codes: M41, M48, M49

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INTRODUCTION

The highly innovative and subjective nature of accrual-based accounting in reporting earnings has led to a drawn-out debate on the propriety of reported earnings and the extent to which they reflect the true economic performance of a firm. High earnings quality is defined as the proportion to which reported earnings reflect the measurable economic performance of the firm, where there are less uncertain interpretations of the reported figures (Barth et al., 2001). Earnings management is the use of accounting techniques to alter financial reports to mislead stakeholders about the firm's economic performance in fortune or misrepresent the firm's underlying profitability (Watts & Zimmerman, 1986), where opportunity costs set the boundary between benefits and losses incurred through earnings manipulation. A corporate governance attribute related to the distribution and construal of financial information is considered to be a highly influential factor for financial reporting quality (Eng et al., 2005). In this context, it is widely perceived that higher quality earnings and governance standards may lead to positive implications for the economy.

The setting for this study is the considerably significant banking sector in Pakistan's atmosphere, where risk-adverse and profit-oriented banks existence can be witnessed. The recent financial debacle followed by economic tribulations has led to closer evaluation of governance and ethics in financial institutions. Greater transparency and accurate financial reporting is the need of the hour in order to achieve better investor confidence, efficient resource allocation, and overall soundness of the economy (Dewatripont et al., 2004). Financial

reports are the chief means of communication for firms and investors must comprehend these reports for decision making. In recent times, the stakeholders especially the equity shareholders, have increasingly become vigilant on the conduct of the board and the financial information disclosed by firms (Tong et al., 2007). The reason behind this is the lower cost of equity capital and better performance for firms exhibiting higher governance and reporting standards (Brown & Caylor, 2009). Financial reporting quality is a significant influence of corporate governance practices (initially discussed by Gompers et al., 2003), in a way that good reporting quality deters managers from opportunistic behaviour and onerous earnings management practices (Akerlof, 1970; Teoh et al., 1998).

Crises in the companies have led researchers to reconsider the effectiveness of corporate governance in terms of oversight of management and its influence on the company's financial reporting activities. Empirical studies concerning corporate governance mechanisms, especially the board of directors, have been growing rapidly since the 1990s. The influence of the board of commissioners and its committees on the company's financial reporting activities has become an interesting discussion since the role of the board is primarily in overseeing and decision-making. They serve as guardians of accountability in the case of management actions and have a vital role in building report with high quality. Compensation and audit committee presence and their activities are expected to improve the two-way relationship between the board and management to increase their concern for financial reports. Empirical research on corporate governance mechanisms in developed countries has shown that events of financial distress and bankruptcy were triggered by the concealment of the real condition of companies through "unhealthy" financial reporting activities. These activities were marked by the act of earnings management, which occurs in two conditions, i.e., to reap the benefits of current owners (income increasing EM) and reduce the possibility of impending current or future losses that might damage the company's condition (income decreasing EM), and increase the fraud of

financial statements. This condition concerns the quality of financial statements, hence the financial and non-financial top management attempt to assess the board and CEO survey in SEC 2004 meeting illustrates that the importance of high-quality financial reports to investor decision-making and lower cost of capital cannot be doubted. This is shown by the high-interest rates on reported earnings.

In the early 2000s, the world was shaken by the collapse of Enron, followed by the collapse of WorldCom shortly after. These were massive corporations with thousands of employees, yet they declared bankruptcy and thousands of employees lost their jobs. Enron was discovered to be involved in fraudulent financial reporting and WorldCom executives were proven to have interfered with the work of others. These financial statement frauds caused substantial losses to public trust and shareholder investments. In addition, other corporate financial scandals occurred in large companies in developed countries, such as Toshiba in Japan (Scott, 2006), HIH Insurance in Australia (Braithwaite, 2003), Daewoo in South Korea (Kim, 2003), and Cadbury in Nigeria (Okaro & Okafor, 2013). These events became the background and main reason for this study. The remaining part of this study consists of a literature review, methodology, findings and discussions, and conclusions and recommendations.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Independence of the board is a non-executive condition, which is declared using a majority of independent directors, and a board whose independent directors meet in the absence of executives. Though it is often assumed that independent directors come together often with or without executives, having a "separate" meeting is useful for assessing the decisions of the executive directors and also for deep discussions about corporate strategy and the interest of the shareholders. This condition is known as management entrenchment. It is not assumed that management entrenches their interest, as many executive decisions are made with the

assumption that it will benefit the company. Independent assessment can still benefit the company by asserting alternative views about what the best interest of the shareholders is.

The definitions of board independence are often tailored to the purpose of the study being conducted, there is a common theme among the differing definitions that suggest an independent board is one free from influence by interested parties. Sometimes board independence is defined by the professional or private interests of the director in question and how these interests conflict with the interests of the organizations' stakeholders. This is related to a legalistic definition of independence and it is suggested that directors who have a conflict of interest should abstain from voting on issues related to the conflicting interests (Baysinger and Butler, 1985). This form of board independence tends to be measured objectively, however, an increase in subjective studies surrounding the social and cognitive psychology of the director has led to definitions of board independence that are more reliant on the quality of judgment exercised by directors.

Board independence is a pivotal concept to the understanding of how the board of directors operates. There are many views concerning what constitutes board independence and what the board of directors is supposed to be independent of. Independent boards are expected to act as watchdog and protector of the shareholders' interest (Dearing & McConnell, 1978), whilst non-independent boards are suspected to more easily accede to management interests (Fama & Jensen, 1983). It has been suggested that the shift in focus from director dependability in the management of the company, to independence from management and focus on shareholders' interests is tied to the different theories of the firm throughout history.

Board independence, according to Finch, is a way in which non-executive directors can act in the best interest of shareholders in shaping the firm's strategic ways to achieve their aims and can also affect the regulation and self-regulation within the industry. This does correlate to the guidance of the Combined Code to non-executive directors, monitoring and strengthening

management performance. The Combined Code, now incorporated into the listing rules, shows that rules are needed to be effective codes, that a rule on the company should comply with the principle of the code, and there should be no specific required rule on the code. This shows that, to Finch, board independence should be allowed for optimal use of methods to reach aims, as opposed to regulatory means, and the monitoring is to ensure better performance to avoid too much regulation.

Within the last years, the term "board independence" has become far more popular, with general articles being written on its characteristics and features. The object of this dissertation is to ascertain its meaning and application to statutory interpretation. Considering the impact the laws have concerning the proportion of executive and non-executive directors and how important it is for companies to comply with corporate governance standards to influence the law-making process to be more favourable to them, as mentioned by Waldman. A study carried out by Finch proposed that organizations that are subject to lessening terms and conditions are likely to trade off some governance standards for others to skew the regulatory policies. The purpose of this extract is to show the different meanings of board independence regarding governance standards, with the hope that they can be enforced to improve the regulatory climate for a wide range of firms.

Conceptual clarity about independence is an essential precursor to research on this topic and efforts to put it into operational effect. For the present project, we define an independent person as one who is not beholden to another, can act on his or her initiative, and is free from the control or influence of others. This encompasses independence in personal thought and action and independence of both condition and behaviour. An independent condition is one in which an individual, corporate body, or other entity is insulated from others to be free from interference in its activities. Behavioural independence means acting according to one's judgment, free from domination from others, and from bowing to pressure or conflicting

interests. Board independence is generally taken to mean the incapacity of an organization or body to act in a manner inconsistent with its objectives. This is presumed to be a positive attribute in that organizations are thought to have been created to do certain things and do them well. However, it also has to be recognized that resignation or failure to attain independence is often a precursor to failure and loss of organizational identity. At worst, it is the discovered price of autonomy.

Independence is a broad, normative concept in contemporary society, and it is applied to a host of entities, actors, and activities. It is also a contested, complex, and elusive concept, often understood in negative terms as the absence of undue influence. This imprecise and incomplete definition is problematic where independence is seen as a key factor in good governance. In this respect, independence is not simply about the absence of malfeasance, but also about the active pursuit of organizational objectives in a manner reasonably free from the dictates of others and from special, particularly vested interests. The issue is not whether board members can be free from influence – as individuals, they bring their values, interests, and perspectives to decision-making. Independence is therefore essentially a relative condition, something that is measurable in degrees, at an individual and collective level.

One of the important components of corporate governance is the establishment of independent boards. This is specifically detailed in the Nigeria Code of Corporate Governance (NCCG, 2018). The effectiveness of independent board members in the quality of earnings entity of the company is reflected in the government regulations. With the determination, this is a regulation on how the financial statements must reflect the actual condition of the company. This is the opening for a study of the influence of independent commissioners' earnings management on the entity quality of the company's financial statements.

The determination of Bapepam No. Kep-04/PM/2004 regarding issuance of the decisions of the board and the board is duty to issuers or public company and decision No. Kep-28/PM/2004 regarding the established committee professional work ethic.

This necessity of behaviour was reflected in the code of corporate governance, entering a new era in 2006. The determination of Bapepam, the approval of the stock exchange, and the law secretary of the Republic of Indonesia No. 8 Year 1995 regarding capital market, it is established that the application of corporate governance is mandatory by all public companies. The reference of the independent commissioners and the audit committee in influencing management's earnings to the entity quality of the companies on financial statements is reflective of the eagerness of the policymakers and the stock exchange in making the betterment of the financial reporting position, one of the closest steps to the investors. It is important to make sure that the financial statements are under the actual condition of the company. This means that any form of earnings management intended to provide a positive upper hand to the company must be eliminated.

Several studies have examined earnings quality in terms of transgressions in financial reporting and accounting practices. Dechow (1995) defines earnings quality as the sustainable reporting of earnings that is a good proxy for cash flow. High-quality earnings provide valuable information for investment and financial decisions. has conceptualized and operationalized earnings quality as the inverse of earnings management using discretionary accruals, while Beatty and Weber (2003) consider that the majority of earnings management behaviour is fraudulent and analyze earnings quality as a form of transgression in financial reporting laws. Measures of earnings management generally associate transgressions in financial reporting laws as increased incidence of accounting errors, violation of debt covenants, or evidence of directors' and executive self-interest. Increased incidence of legal action in response to accounting transgressions suggests that there is a threshold whereby low earnings quality

destroys shareholder wealth and is detrimental to society. This would assume that a correlation between increased monitoring of management and intended improvement in earnings quality is dominant. This leads to predictions that changes in board structure legislation will affect earnings quality for firms that must comply. Firms altering their board structure may incur both initial transition costs and long-term implications on board expertise and composition. These costs incurred from adverse selection and the opportunity cost of governance can be viewed as an investment for firms to alter operational efficiency and capital allocation decisions. Support for the relation between board structure and earnings quality will enable inferences concerning the effectiveness and implications of governance changes on these firms.

Various key assumptions are made by the general public and accounting regulators concerning board structure and earnings quality. The corporate governance movement presumes that boards established with an independent majority are more efficient monitors of management. Compared to executive boards, independent boards have suggested that governance performance and board monitoring will be higher in situations where the board is predominantly composed of independent directors. To the extent that the quality of accounting in financial reports is a reflection of board monitoring, one would hypothesize that there is some relation between board independence and earnings quality. Regulators assuming this relation have implemented changes in board structure legislation. The Sarbanes Oxley Act mandates that boards must be composed of at least 50% independent directors, while the proposed changes to NZX listing rules have suggested that there should be a majority of independent directors.

The introduction section of the report will aim to give the reader a better understanding of the role of board committees in today's corporate governance. It will give an insight into the decisions made by the board of directors and how this has changed since the Sarbanes-Oxley legislation. It will introduce how these changes in corporate governance have led to stepped-

up supervision of top management and increased monitoring of their activities. This will all be linked to the decisions affecting earnings and the relevance this has to the rest of the report. This section will lay the foundation for the rest of the report to investigate board decisions and earnings more thoroughly.

When it comes to the earnings of a business or a company, it is considered the most important indicator that will reflect the overall business performance and its prospects. Earning is the output result between its input process and the output result can be in many forms. It can be in short-term (temporary) earnings which will not be recorded as the company's actual performance and/or long-term (permanent) earnings which are expected to reflect the true earnings of a company. Temporary earnings can be created by an action of accruals and will not reflect the company's performance. Long-term earning is the result of a successful action taken by the company in all business stages. The indicator of short-term and long-term earnings can differ by its amount and its posture. However, the company's relative success and failure is said to happen if there is a decrease in any form of earnings. Quality earnings should reflect a relative of an accumulated long-term earning and avoid timing issues that can have effects on the company. So, the assessment of company earnings should be measured by comparing its result of cash flow and the prospects of the company in many stages. Assessment of its earnings can be conducted by various parties, but stockholders are the ones who are mostly concerned about this matter. Earning provides current stockholders prospects and it will also affect the demands of prospective stockholders to buy the company's stock. Assessment of a company's earnings can be affected by the information of actual earnings that's been prepared by the company and will be disclosed by its financial statement. The importance of ascertaining the quality of earnings has increased in recent years due to the data mining financial report scandals that have occurred. Companies are very capable of manipulating revenues and expenses to meet earnings targets. This is usually done at the time of upper-level management

turnover when their performance is assessed based on earnings in incentive compensation plans. High-ranking officers can capitalize on higher bonuses if earnings targets are achieved. Market pressure and the nature of the stock market also cause companies to announce earnings that are above the actual earnings to meet the expectations of investors and to maintain a competitive stock price. When companies partake in these activities it leads to adverse effects because overstating on earnings will produce lower quality earnings and will give an unsustainable condition compared to the prior period. Announcing earnings that are above actual earnings will place companies at risk for future negative abnormal returns when the market learns of the misdeed. Manipulation of earnings can confuse investors and affect their decisions on current and future investments in the company's stock. This can also affect creditors and those who are seeking long-term employment with the company. Due to these reasons, a company needs to provide a clear representation of their financial position and the results of their performance.

Figure 1. The Analytical Framework

Source: The Authors (2024)

Furthermore, agency theory and stakeholder theory provide the theoretical foundations of this paper. Jensen and Meckling (1976) describe the agency relationship as a relationship between the company owner (principal) and the agent, with the delegation of the decision-making authority to the agent. In an agency relationship, there may be a conflict of interest between the principal and the agent. Shareholders demand increased corporate profitability and dividends, while the manager is an agent motivated to maximize the fulfillment of economic and psychological needs. Based on agency and principal relationships, management is encouraged to perform earnings management in presenting financial statements. For that, one of the ways that can be used to monitor contract issues between management and investors and limit the opportunistic behaviour of management is through the implementation of corporate governance mechanisms of which boards and their committees are part.

In addition, Freeman (1984) concluded that the real purpose of a company is to meet the needs of stakeholders, i.e. those affected by the decisions taken by the company. Gray et al. (1995) said that the survival of a company depends on the support of its stakeholders, and that support should be sought so that the company should seek that support. The stronger the stakeholders, the more the companies are trying to adapt. Stakeholder theory is important in this research because the theory is related to the parties that are interested in the company; those who will be affected and influenced by the activities of the company, such as accountability of management to stakeholders in the form of quality earnings.

In empirical studies on the nexus between the board and its committees and earnings quality, several works exist both in and outside Nigeria. For example, Wild (1996) provides empirical evidence on the association between audit committee formation and the quality of accounting earnings by assessing the effectiveness of the audit committee in discharging these responsibilities by comparing the quality, or informativeness, of earnings reports before and after audit committee formation. The results show a significant increase in the market's reaction

to earnings reports after the formation of the audit committee. Specifically, the reaction to earnings reports is more than 20 percent greater after the formation of the committee than before.

Lin et al. (2006) examine the association between the characteristics of audit committees (size, independence, financial expertise, activity, and stock ownership) and earnings restatement – a direct measure of earnings management. Univariate correlations and multivariate statistical analyses are performed. In particular, a multivariate logistic regression model is used. Evidence suggests a negative association between the size of audit committees and the occurrence of earnings restatement. The remaining four audit committee characteristics are not found to have a significant impact on the quality of reported earnings.

Hashim and Devi (2008) examine the relationship between board characteristics (i.e. board independence, CEO duality, board size, board meeting, and board tenure) and earnings quality. Data from 280 non-financial companies listed on Bursa Malaysia's Main Board for the year 2004 was used. A significant association was found between board tenure and earnings quality. In addition, a positive significant association was found between outside board ownership and earnings quality. However, no significant relationship was found between the board of directors' independence and earnings quality.

He et al. (2009) examine two oversight components, board characteristics and audit committee characteristics. For each component, they summarize associations between variables contributing to monitoring effectiveness and three presumptive FRQ monitoring outcomes: (1) ex post consequences of low FRQ, such as financial reporting fraud; (2) earnings management measures, such as abnormal accruals; and (3) perceived informativeness of financial reports, manifest in earnings-returns associations, earnings response coefficients, and analyst perceptions of FRQ. Their classification scheme provides a coherent framework for

synthesizing the implications of empirical findings, highlighting the role of different corporate governance variables in enhancing different aspects of FRQ.

Dimitropoulos and Asteriou (2010) examine how the informational quality of annual accounting earnings, varies according to the size and composition of the board of directors of publicly listed firms within the Greek capital market. Data analysis over five years (2000–2004) revealed that the informativeness of annual accounting earnings is positively related to the fraction of outside directors serving on the board, but it is not related to board size. Additionally, firms with a higher proportion of outside board members proved to be more conservative when reporting bad news but on the contrary, they do not display greater timeliness on the recognition of good news. Finally, firms with a higher proportion of outside directors' report earnings of higher quality compared to firms with a low proportion of outside directors.

Wan Ismail (2011) investigates whether corporate governance is associated with earnings quality. This study uses a panel sample of 527 publicly traded firms over the period 2003-2008 from the Malaysia Stock Exchange (Bursa Malaysia). This study finds that the earnings quality of firms in Malaysia is positively associated with the size and independence of the audit committee and negatively associated with the size of the board of directors.

Al-Dhamari and Ku Ismail (2012) examine the relationship between board characteristics and earnings quality after the Malaysian Code of Corporate Governance was amended in 2007. It uses heteroskedasticity-corrected least square regressions upon a sample of Malaysian firms listed in 2008 and 2009. They find that the quality of earnings is higher for firms with independent chairmen than those with non-independent chairmen. However, in contradiction to our expectations are inconclusive results on board independence. The results also demonstrate that investors do not perceive board size as a good indicator of quality earnings.

Garcia et al. (2012) analyse the relation between characteristics of the audit committee and earnings management measured as abnormal accruals to test the quality of financial statements. Using a sample of 108 non-financial Spanish companies that traded on the Madrid Stock Exchange between 2003 and 2006 (432 observations), they found that the size and number of meetings of the audit committee had a significant negative association with earnings manipulations.

Nelson and Devi (2013) investigate the relationship between audit committee expertise and financial reporting quality. Based on two theories, the resource dependence theory and agency theory, the study examines the association of audit committee experts with financial reporting quality, proxied by earnings management. Samples involved 2008 financial data of 300 firms that were ranked by highest market capitalization. In total, four types of expertise are developed based on academic qualification, professional qualification, and work experience. The presence of non-accounting experts and accounting experts is significant in reducing the magnitude of earnings management. Other than that, leverage and firm size are also found to be significant.

Fodio et al. (2013) investigate the effect of corporate governance mechanisms on the reported earnings quality of listed Insurance companies in Nigeria. Using twenty-five (25) quoted insurance firms during the period 2007-2010, the study regressed five governance mechanisms on reported earnings quality proxy. Multiple regressions were employed for the analysis using the software SPSS version 17.0. The study finds that board size, board independence, and audit committee size are negatively and significantly associated with earnings management while audit committee independence and independent external audit have a positive relationship with discretionary accruals.

Alves (2014) examines whether board independence improves earnings quality by reducing earnings management in Portugal, a country with significantly different institutional and legal characteristics from the Anglo-Saxon countries. Using ordinary least squares (OLS) and two-

stage least squares (2SLS) techniques to control potential simultaneity problems between board independence and earnings quality, the study found evidence that independent board members improve earnings quality by reducing earnings management for a sample of Portuguese listed firms. This result suggests that strengthening the independence of boards by appointing more independent board members is a positive step toward improving earnings quality.

Piyawiboon (2015) investigates the relationships between the board audit committee and the earning quality of the listed firms in 4 industrial groups in the Stock Exchange of Thailand (SET) which are: Agro and Food, Resource, Technology, and Consumer goods from 2009 to 2013. The results show that the relationship between the efficiency of the Board Audit Committee and the Audit Quality was not found and cannot be concluded.

Al-Rassas (2015) examines the relationship between internal monitoring mechanisms, namely, board of directors, audit committee, and earnings quality based on agency theory and resource dependence theory. The sample of the study is 2,036 firm-year observations on the Main Market of Bursa Malaysia for the period of 2009 to 2012. Two discretionary accruals models were used to measure earnings quality. This study reveals that board size, audit committee financial expertise, increase the quality of earnings. However, board independence, board financial expertise, audit committee's chairman, audit committee meeting, and audit committee score reduce earnings quality.

Khalil and Ozkan (2016) investigate the relationship between board independence, audit quality, and earnings management. They test whether firm-level corporate governance provisions matter in an emerging market setting characterized by weak legal enforcement and inadequate external discipline by the market for corporate control. Their results cast doubt on the notion that a higher ratio of non-executive members is associated with lower earnings management. They find that the effect of board independence on earnings management

practices is contingent on the levels of ownership held by executive directors and large shareholders, as well as the composition of the audit committee.

Zgarni et al. (2016) examine relationships between audit committee effectiveness and financial reporting quality in Tunisia. This study examines the role of audit committee effectiveness on financial reporting quality particularly to mitigate the earnings management in the Tunisian companies before and after financial security law adoption. The study uses an ordinary least squares regression model to investigate the effect of audit committee characteristics, audit quality attributes, and the interaction between these two overseeing mechanisms on earnings management for a sample of 29 non-financial listed Tunisian firms during the period 2001-2009. The results document a substitute effect between the effective audit committee to reduce the discretionary accruals before the enforcement of law no. 2005-96 dealing with the financial securities. The authors find a score of the audit committee's effectiveness in constraining earnings management.

Abbadi et al. (2016) investigate the effect of corporate governance quality on earnings management in Jordan. Using a panel data set of all industrial and service firms listed on Amman Stock Exchange during the period 2009-2013; this paper provides evidence that earnings management is affected negatively by corporate governance quality. In particular; the results show that earnings management is affected negatively by overall categories of governance index represented by a board of directors, board meeting, Audit and nomination, and compensation committee.

Kent et al. (2016) examine the effectiveness of voluntary governance mechanisms in Australia. This study identifies similar choices of corporate governance by Australian firms and tests the effectiveness of the choices made based on the earnings quality of reported firms. Cluster analysis is conducted using governance best practice variables, firm size and an earnings quality variable. This paper's results support the voluntary governance approach for smaller

firms, but suggest that mandatory governance requirements could be beneficial for larger firms. Evidence suggests that a benefit accrues for larger firms with the adoption of governance best practice.

Hoang et al. (2017) investigate the effect of board diversity on earnings quality in a sample of Vietnamese-listed firms. They find a significant, positive linear relationship between diversity of boards and earnings quality, while the relationship between diversity in boards and earnings quality is non-linear, with a U-shaped curve.

Katmon and Al-Farooque (2017) investigate the impact of internal corporate governance on the relation between disclosure quality and earnings management in the UK listed companies, in particular whether governance mechanisms have deterrent effect on earnings management similar to firms' disclosure quality. Their findings in the OLS and sensitivity analyses using Heckman Procedure and 2SLS regressions consistently report a significant negative association between earnings management and disclosure quality for all proxies in restraining earnings management. In contrast, corporate governance variables are mostly insignificantly related to earnings management.

Otuya et al. (2017) examine the relationship between earnings management and quality of corporate governance in Nigeria. The study adopted the content analysis research design and data were obtained from financial statements of sampled companies. The population of the study consists of all companies listed in the Nigeria Stock Exchange. The study using data from annual reports of manufacturing companies for the period 2012 to 2016 analyzed some simple descriptive and correlation statistics and used regressions to examine the relationship between the variables highlighted in the study. The study showed that quality of corporate governance, audit committee strength and executive compensation have a significant negative relationship with earnings management.

Chen and Komal (2018) reconcile through meta-analysis the results of 90 studies with 165,529 firm-year observations concerning the relationship between audit committee financial expertise and earnings quality. The results show that audit committee financial expertise has a positive relationship with earnings quality and that accounting financial experts have a stronger relationship with earnings quality than non-accounting financial experts.

Agyei-Mensah and Yeboah (2019) investigate the influence of audit committee effectiveness on earnings management by firms listed on the Ghana Stock Exchange. The study uses 180 firm-year observations for the period 2013-2017 for firms listed on the Ghana Stock Exchange. Descriptive analysis was performed to provide the background statistics of the variables examined. This was followed by regression analysis, which forms the main data analysis. The results of multivariate regression analysis indicated that audit committee financial expertise, audit committee prior experience, and audit committee size have a significant negative relationship with discretionary accruals as a proxy for earnings management. On the other hand, no significant relationship was found between audit committee independence and audit committee meetings and the level of discretionary accruals.

Kontesa et al. (2020) examine the relationship between board ownership and firm earnings quality with different controlling shareholders for a sample of 252 listed firms in Indonesia over the period 2011–2017. This study uses a two-step dynamic generalized method of moments panel regression to estimate the board capital effect on earnings quality. All financial data was from the annual report. The findings of this study report that board ownership has a significant effect on earnings quality. Higher board ownership may result in better earnings quality. In further investigation, this study finds that boards with higher education backgrounds tend to have better earnings quality. Meanwhile, boards with highly experienced members tend to have bad earnings quality.

Weber (2020) investigates the influence of audit committee expertise, i.e., the financial knowledge, educational level, and industry background of audit committee members on earnings quality in the German two-tier system. The sampling frame is 610 firm-year observations of German-listed firms, from 2007 to 2013. The results of a multivariate regression analysis reveal that higher levels of financial expertise and advanced educational backgrounds of audit committee members are significantly associated with higher earnings quality. Findings suggest that audit committees with greater levels of financial expertise have more specific knowledge and experience in understanding accounting policies as well as better quality in overseeing the financial reporting process. Moreover, results reveal that educational level has a positive impact on audit committee effectiveness as it enables better performance abilities.

Pratiwim and Pralita (2021) provide empirical evidence on the influence of corporate governance mechanisms (audit committee, independence board of commissioner), accounting conservatism, and company size on earnings quality. The sample used in this research are manufacturing company listed in the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) in 2016-2018 using purposive sampling and obtained 29 companies. Data were analyzed using the multiple regression method. The finding of this research accounting conservatism and company size partially have a negative significant effect on earnings quality. The audit committee and independence board of the commissioner have no significant effect on earnings quality. In addition, corporate governance mechanisms, accounting conservatism, and company size simultaneously have a significant effect on earnings quality.

Efenyumi (2022) evaluates how the characteristics of risk management committees (independence and diligence) impact listed companies' earnings quality with 70 firms for ten years (2012-2021). According to the OLS analysis used to analyze the hypothesis, risk

management committee characteristics have no appreciable impact on the listed firms' profitability reporting.

Elhaj et al. (2022) examine the role of the risk management committee in addressing Real Earnings Management (REM). However, empirical studies on the role of RMC's attributes in the reporting quality and performance of publicly owned companies are still underdeveloped. This study employs Feasible Generalized Least Square (FGLS) regression to investigate the effects of RMC on REM practice in Malaysian publicly listed companies. Using a sample of 438 firm-year observations from 2016 to 2018, the research findings reveal that RMC size, diligence, and members' qualifications have negative effects on REM. Furthermore, the results show that RMC independence does not affect REM. Based on these mix results from empirical studies, we hypothesize that:

H₁: The Board of directors has a statistically significant effect on earnings quality.

H₂: The audit committee has a statistically significant effect on earnings quality.

H₃: The nomination committee has a statistically significant effect on earnings quality.

H₄: The remuneration committee has a statistically significant effect on earnings quality.

H₅: The risk committee has a statistically significant effect on earnings quality.

METHODOLOGY

This section covers the research design, population and sample of the study, model specification, variables, definitions, and measurements, including a priori expectations, data collection technique, methods of data analysis, diagnostic tests, and criteria for acceptance or rejection of hypotheses. Thus, the research design is ex post facto, that is, the study uses historical data. The population and sample of the study are 154 publicly listed firms on the floor of the Nigerian Exchange (NGX) as of 31 December 2022. See Table 1.

Table 1. Population/Sample Size

Serial	Sector	Number
1	Agriculture	6
2	Conglomerates	6
3	Construction/Real estate	9
4	Consumer goods	21
5	Financial services	47
6	Healthcare	8
7	Information & communications technology	8
8	Industrial goods	13
9	Natural resources	4
10	Oil and gas	10
11	Services	22
	Total	154

Source: Extracts from NGX (2024)

The model is specified as follows according to xx (xx), after accounting for the control variables.

$$EQ_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 BODI_{i,t} + \beta_2 AUCI_{i,t} + \beta_3 NMCI_{i,t} + \beta_4 RECI_{i,t} + \beta_5 RIC I_{i,t} + \beta_6 FSIZ_{i,t} + \beta_7 PROF_{i,t} + \beta_8 LAGE_{i,t} + \beta_9 LEVG_{i,t} + \mu_{i,t}$$

Based on the model, EQ is earnings quality, BODI is a board of directors' independence, AUCI is audit committee independence, NMCI is nomination committee independence, RECI is remuneration committee independence, RIC I is risk committee independence, FSIZ is firm size, PROF is profitability, LAGE is listing age, and LEVG is leverage. Furthermore, i is firm

script, t is time script, α is constant, β_{1-9} are beta coefficients to be estimated, and μ is the error term.

These variables are measured in greater detail as indicated in Table 2.

Table 2. Variables, Measurements and Signs

Serial	Variables	Measurements	Sign
1	Y, Earnings quality	Kothari discretionary accrual score	
2	X ₁ , Board independence	Measured as the non-executive board of directors divided by total board size (%).	+
3	X ₂ , Audit committee independence	Measured as the number of non-directors and non-executive directors in the audit committee divided by audit committee members size (%).	+
4	X ₃ , Nomination committee independence	Measured as the number of non-directors and non-executive directors in the nomination committee divided by nomination committee members size (%).	+
5	X ₄ , Remuneration Committee independence	Measured as the number of non-directors and non-executive directors in the remuneration committee divided by remuneration committee members size (%).	+
6	X ₅ , Risk Committee independence	Measured as the number of non-directors and non-executive directors in the risk committee divided by risk committee members size (%).	+
7	X ₆ , Firm size	Measured as a natural log of total assets.	+
8	X ₇ , Profitability	Measured as profit after tax divided by total assets (%).	+
9	X ₈ , Listing age	Measured as several years a company is trading on the stock exchange.	+
10	X ₉ , Leverage	Measured as total liabilities divided by total assets.	-

Source: The Authors (2024)

Thus, our a priori expectations are as follows:

X₁>0, an increase in board independence, will increase earnings quality.

X₂>0, an increase in audit committee independence, will increase earnings quality.

X₃>0, an increase in nomination committee independence, will increase earnings quality.

X₄>0, an increase in remuneration committee independence, will increase earnings quality.

X₅>0, an increase in risk committee independence, will increase earnings quality.

X₆>0, an increase in firm size, will increase earnings quality.

$X_7 > 0$, an increase in profitability, will increase earnings quality.

$X_8 > 0$, an increase in listing age, will increase earnings quality.

$X_9 > 0$, an increase in leverage, will reduce earnings quality.

The data of the study are collected as follows. Data on earnings management was handpicked and modelled based on the Kothari discretionary accrual score. The data on boards, their committees, and listing age are collected using content analysis. The data on profitability and firm size are collected based on ratios. All the data are collected from the sampled companies' financial statements. Financial statements are formal communications channels authorized by the Companies and Allied Matters Act (1990 as amended) in Nigeria to communicate with stakeholders. Several past studies have used companies' financial statements (Aktan, 2009; Alattar & Al-Khater, 2008; Alfraih, 2016; Alrshah, 2015; Argiles & Slof, 2003; Beasley, 1996; Cole et al., 2009; Hai et al., 2015; Kalantonis et al., 2009; Secinaro et al., 2020).

Furthermore, we use frequency distribution, descriptive statistics, correlation analysis techniques, and multiple regression analysis techniques to analyze the data of this study. We also carry out two post-estimation tests (heteroskedasticity test and multicollinearity test) to ensure that the regression analysis results of the study are robust. We adopt R^2 to explain the joint effects of the independent and control variables on the variations in earning quality. Furthermore, we use a t-test to accept or reject the individual independent variables, and an F-test for model fitness. Overall, we accept or reject hypotheses and post-estimation tests based on a 5 percent level of significance.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

In this section, first, we examine the frequency table of our variables of interest relating to our sampled firms. A frequency distribution table is a table that summarizes values and their frequency. It is a useful way to organize data if you have a list of numbers that represent the frequency of a certain outcome in a sample. A frequency distribution table has two columns: frequency and percentage. The results of the frequency distribution are presented in Table 3 as follows.

Table 3. *Frequency distribution*

Serial	Variable	Frequency	Percentage
1	EQ	2,310	100
2	BODI	2,310	100
3	AUCI	2,310	100
4	NMCI	2,310	100
5	RECI	2,310	100
6	RICI	2,310	100
7	FSIZ	2,310	100
8	PROF	2,310	100
9	LAGE	2,310	100
10	LEVG	2,310	100

Source: STATA 18.4 Outputs

Following the results in Table 3, it can be observed that the number of observations is 2,310 and that all the variables of the study have balanced data throughout the study (2008-2022). Table 4 presents the results of the descriptive analysis, and covers the number of observations, the central mean, standard deviations (spread or volatility), minimum mean, and maximum mean.

Table 4. Descriptive statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
EQ	2,310	.007	.008	0	.063
BODI	2,310	.218	.102	.053	.545
AUCI	2,310	50.339	5.044	42.857	100
NMCI	2,310	86.545	18.346	0	100
RECI	2,310	89.364	12.912	60	100
RICI	2,310	65.469	16.943	25	100
FSIZ	2,310	9.276	.43	8.119	10.098
PROF	2,310	11.883	18.243	-91.95	122.8
LAGE	2,310	22.827	15.081	2	50
LEVG	2,310	.929	.258	.717	2.547

Source: STATA 18.4 Outputs

From the results in Table 4, the number of observations is again 2,310 (15 years x 154 firms), the mean of earnings quality is .007, the mean of board of directors' independence is 21.8 percent, the mean of audit committee independence is 50.339 percent, the mean of nomination committee independence is 86.545 percent, the mean of remuneration committee independence is 89.364, the mean of risk committee independence is 65.469 percent, the mean of firm size is 9.276 times, the mean of profitability is 11.883 percent, the mean of listing age is 23 years, and the mean of leverage is 92.9 percent. In examining the bivariate association between earnings quality and independent and control variables, we employ the Pearson (pairwise) correlation coefficient (correlation matrix), and the results are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Pearson (Pairwise) Correlation Matrix

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)
(1) EQ	1.000									
(2) BODI	0.369*	1.000								
	(0.000)									
(3) AUCI	0.318*	0.002	1.000							
	(0.000)	(0.984)								
(4) NMCI	0.030	-0.033	0.109	1.000						
	(0.759)	(0.732)	(0.258)							
(5) RECI	0.118	-0.140	-0.075	-0.080	1.000					
	(0.219)	(0.144)	(0.433)	(0.407)						
(6) RICI	0.444*	-0.219*	-0.094	-0.086	0.202*	1.000				
	(0.000)	(0.021)	(0.329)	(0.369)	(0.034)					
(7) FSIZ	0.338*	0.269*	0.126	0.105	-0.085	-0.201*	1.000			
	(0.000)	(0.004)	(0.190)	(0.277)	(0.375)	(0.036)				
(8) PROF	-0.018	0.021	-0.005	-0.079	-0.055	0.114	0.046	1.000		
	(0.849)	(0.824)	(0.955)	(0.414)	(0.565)	(0.236)	(0.632)			
(9) LAGE	0.059	0.302*	-0.085	0.151	0.390*	0.108	-0.189*	-0.077	1.000	
	(0.540)	(0.001)	(0.375)	(0.116)	(0.000)	(0.261)	(0.048)	(0.426)		
(10) LEVG	-0.463*	-0.213*	-0.063	-0.143	0.207*	0.193*	-0.417*	0.000	0.148	1.000
	(0.000)	(0.026)	(0.513)	(0.136)	(0.030)	(0.043)	(0.000)	(0.996)	(0.123)	

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Source: STATA 18.4 Outputs

Following the results in Table 5, it can be said that the bivariate relationship between earnings quality and the board of directors' independence is positive (.369) and statistically significant (.000). Also, the bivariate relationship between earnings quality and the audit committee independence is positive (.318) and statistically significant (.000). In contrast, however, the bivariate relationship between earnings quality and the nomination committee independence is positive (.030) and statistically insignificant (.759). In the same manner, the bivariate

relationship between earnings quality and remuneration committee independence is positive (.118) and statistically insignificant (.219). However, the bivariate relationship between earnings quality and risk committee independence is positive (.444) and statistically significant (.000). On the four control variables, the bivariate relationship between earnings quality and firm size is positive (.338) and statistically significant (.000). In complete contrast, the bivariate relationship between earnings quality and profitability is negative (-.018) and statistically insignificant (.849). In almost the same manner, the bivariate relationship between earnings quality and listing age is positive (.059) and statistically insignificant (.540). However, in line with our a priori expectation, leverage shows a negative (-.463) and statistically significant (.000) value with earnings quality.

Furthermore, in testing the hypotheses for this study, we used the Generalised Method of Moments (GMM) regression model. The model focuses on estimating the effect of the board and its committees' independence on earnings quality, after accounting for political connections (firm size), present and potential owners (profitability), listing age (experience), and lenders and creditors (leverage). This means that the board and its committees' independence are our independent variables while earnings quality is our dependent variable. The GMM model, which is generally used for panel data, provides consistent results in the presence of different sources of endogeneity, namely unobserved heterogeneity, simultaneity, and dynamic endogeneity (Wintoki et al., 2012). Furthermore, the generalized method of moments is a statistical method that combines observed economic data with information in population moment conditions to produce estimates of the unknown parameters of this economic model. Several scholars and researchers have used the Generalised Method of Moments in their studies (Hall, 2003; Imbens, 2002; Ogaki, 1993; Teritlak, 2016; Ullah et al., 2018; Syofya, 2022; Sutradhar et al., 2008; Susilo et al., 2020; Warsono et al., 2014; Wooldridge, 2001). The GMM regression analysis results are presented in Table 6.

Table 6. GMM regression results

GMM estimation

Number of parameters = 10

Number of moments = 10

Initial weight matrix: Unadjusted

Number of obs = 2,310

GMM weight matrix: Robust

EQ	Coef.	Robust Std. Err.	z	P>z	[95% Conf.	Interval]
BODI	.024520	.007453	3.29	0.001	-.0049607	.0242544
AUCI	.0005100	.0000619	8.24	0.000	-.0001062	.0001364
NMCI	.0000617	.0000323	1.91	0.056	-1.52e-06	.000125
RECI	.0000768	.0000644	1.19	0.233	-.0000494	.000203
RICI	.0000716	.0000336	2.13	0.033	-.0001375	-5.75e-06
FSIZ	.0048205	.0015519	3.11	0.002	-.0078622	-.0017788
PROF	6.72e-06	.000027	0.25	0.803	-.0000461	.0000596
LAGE	.0000751	.0000551	1.36	0.173	-.0001832	.000033
LEVG	-.013476	.0082199	-1.64	0.101	-.0026346	.0295866
/b0	.0303608	.016048	1.89	0.059	-.0010926	.0618143
R ²	.2921					
Prob>z	.0000					
Hetest	.0000					
Mean VIF	1.30					

Source: STATA 18.4 Outputs

From the results in Table 6, we observe that board of directors' independence shows a positive beta coefficient (.024520) and a statistically significant (.001) effect on earnings quality. By

extension, a unit increase in board of directors' independence will lead to about 2.453 percent improvement in earnings quality. Similarly, audit committee independence shows a positive beta coefficient (.0005100) and a statistically significant (.000) effect on earnings quality, and by extension, a unit increase in audit committee independence will lead to about .051 percent improvement in earnings quality. In contrast, both nomination and remuneration committees' independence show no statistically significant in relation to earnings quality. Furthermore, risk committee independence shows a positive beta coefficient (.0000716) and a statistically significant (.033) effect on earnings quality, and by implication, a unit increase in risk committee independence will lead to about .00716 percent improvement in earnings quality. Of the four control variables, only firm size shows a positive beta coefficient (.0048205) and a statistically significant (.002) effect on earnings quality, and by extension, a unit increase in firm size will lead to about 0.48205 percent improvement in earnings quality. Thus, Hypotheses 1, 2, and 5 are hereby accepted, while Hypotheses 3 and 4 are hereby rejected.

On the coefficient of determination, which is represented by R^2 , the joint effect of independent and control variables in explaining the variations in earnings quality is 29.21 percent. In the words of Cohen (1988), $R^2 < 0.02$ - very weak; $0.02 < R^2 < 0.13$ - weak; $0.13 < R^2 < 0.26$ - moderate, and $R^2 > 0.26$ - substantial. By these interpretations, it means that our R^2 is substantial. The test of fitness of the model, which is measured by the Prob>z is 0.0000, which is statistically significant, suggesting that our model is fit to be used to explain the variations in earnings quality. In the presence of heteroskedasticity, the use of robust standard errors has taken care of it. Finally, on the test of multicollinearity, the mean of variance inflation factor is 1.30, which is less than the 10, threshold, for the presence of multicollinearity according to Alauddin and Nghiem (2010).

Furthermore, while these results are consistent with our a priori expectations, they are however mixed findings, relative to past empirical studies. During the course of this study, several ideas

and potential research areas have been identified. The purpose of this section is to serve as a source of inspiration for further researchers. In this manner, the following are the suggestions for further research. Only fifteen years data were taken for the study, so the data is not sufficient, future research may increase the number of years covered. There are so several measures of earnings quality that are available, but this study considers only Kothari discretionary accrual score. Only four control variables were considered in this study, future research may consider others, such as audit quality, liquidity, sales growth, and several others. Our study results show that the R^2 value is 29.21%, further research is expected to be able to add other firm characteristic variables as control variables that may influence the R^2 .

CONCLUSION

This study investigates the effects of the board of directors and its committees on earnings quality of 154 publicly listed companies in Nigeria, for 15 years (2008-2022). The number of observations was 2,310 (15 years x 154 companies). The mean of earnings quality is .007, the mean of board of directors' independence is 21.8 percent, the mean of audit committee independence is 50.339 percent, the mean of nomination committee independence is 86.545 percent, the mean of remuneration committee independence is 89.364, the mean of risk committee independence is 65.469 percent, the mean of firm size is 9.276 times, the mean of profitability is 11.883 percent, the mean of listing age is 23 years, and the mean of leverage is 92.9 percent.

Furthermore, the bivariate relationship between earnings quality and the board of directors' independence is positive (.369) and statistically significant (.000). Also, the bivariate relationship between earnings quality and the audit committee independence is positive (.318) and statistically significant (.000). In contrast, however, the bivariate relationship between earnings quality and the nomination committee independence is positive (.030) and statistically insignificant (.759). In the same manner, the bivariate relationship between earnings quality

and remuneration committee independence is positive (.118) and statistically insignificant (.219). However, the bivariate relationship between earnings quality and risk committee independence is positive (.444) and statistically significant (.000). On the four control variables, the bivariate relationship between earnings quality and firm size is positive (.338) and statistically significant (.000). In complete contrast, the bivariate relationship between earnings quality and profitability is negative (-.018) and statistically insignificant (.849). In almost the same manner, the bivariate relationship between earnings quality and listing age is positive (.059) and statistically insignificant (.540). However, in line with our a priori expectation, leverage shows a negative (-.463) and statistically significant (.000) value with earnings quality.

Also, we observe that the board of directors' independence shows a positive beta coefficient (.024520) and a statistically significant (.001) effect on earnings quality. By extension, a unit increase in board of directors' independence will lead to about 2.453 percent improvement in earnings quality. Similarly, audit committee independence shows a positive beta coefficient (.0005100) and a statistically significant (.000) effect on earnings quality, and by extension, a unit increase in audit committee independence will lead to about .051 percent improvement in earnings quality. In contrast, both nomination and remuneration committees' independence show no statistically significant in relation to earnings quality. Furthermore, risk committee independence shows a positive beta coefficient (.0000716) and a statistically significant (.033) effect on earnings quality, and by implication, a unit increase in risk committee independence will lead to about .00716 percent improvement in earnings quality. Of the four control variables, only firm size shows a positive beta coefficient (.0048205) and a statistically significant (.002) effect on earnings quality, and by extension, a unit increase in firm size will lead to about 0.48205 percent improvement in earnings quality. These results have contributed to our understanding of the nexus between the board and its committees' independence and

earnings quality literature. Regulators and other stakeholders will benefit from the results of the study in terms of performance and policy improvements. Also, future research will have this paper as a reference material to consult with.

REFERENCES

- Abbadi, S. S., Hijazi, Q. F., & Al-Rahahleh, A. S. (2016). Corporate governance quality and earnings management: Evidence from Jordan. *Australasian Accounting, Business and Finance Journal*, 10(2), 54-75.
- Abbas, S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Audit committee and financial statement fraud likelihood. *Journal of Contemporary Accounting and Economics*, 19(2), 100365.
- Abdullahi, K., Musa, R., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Are CEOs hedge against share price fall? *Accounting and Business Research*, 53(5), 243-263.
- Abdulwahab, A. I., Bala, H., Adamu, A., Yahaya, O. A., & Khatoon, G. (2023). Does board independence moderate the nexus involving ownership formation and financial performance? Evidence from Nigerian Exchange Group. *POLAC International Journal of Economic and Management Science*, 9(2), 1-9.
- Abdulwahab, A. I., Bala, H., Yahaya, O. A., & Abdullahi, M. (2023). Corporate governance committees and sustainability reporting of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (ISSN: 2454-6186)*, 7(7), 1761-1770.
- Abdulwahab, A. I., Bala, H., Yahaya, O. A., & Khatoon, G. (2023). Moderating effect of risk committee presence on the nexus between CEO characteristics and dividend policy: Evidence from listed companies in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Management Sciences*, 24(1), 165-176.
- Abubakar, A. A., Yahaya, O. A., & Joshua, S. G. (2023). Board characteristics and financial performance. *Asian-Pacific Journal of Financial Studies*, 52, 7-19.
- Abubakar, B. A., Yahaya, O. A., & Nma, A. M. (2021). Board features and financial performance of Nigerian banks. *Intl Journal of Finance & Banking Studies*, 10(1).
- Adewinmisi, G. O., Ahmed, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Audit committee independence and audit quality of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 1(3), 16-26.
- Agyei-Mensah, B. K., & Yeboah, M. (2019). Effective audit committee, audit quality and earnings management: evidence from the Ghana Stock Exchange. *International Journal of Managerial and Financial Accounting*, 11(2), 93-112.
- Ahmed, D., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Institutional and board ownership and corporate financial performance in Nigeria. *Advances in Business Research*, 14, 111-132.
- Ahmed, Y., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). New insights on board structure and income smoothing hypothesis. *Asian Economic and Financial Review*, 4(1), 784-803.
- Alauddin, M., & Nghiem, H. S. (2010). Do instructional attributes pose multicollinearity problems? An empirical exploration. *Economic Analysis and Policy*, 40(3), 351-361.
- Al-dhamari, R., & Ku Ismail, K. N. I. (2012). The association between board characteristics and earnings quality: Malaysian evidence. *Jurnal Pengurusan*, 41, 43-55.
- Al-Rassas, A. H. (2015). Internal monitoring mechanisms and earnings quality: Empirical evidence from Malaysia. *Universiti Utara Malaysia*.

- Alves, S. (2014). The effect of board independence on the earnings quality: evidence from Portuguese listed companies. *Australasian Accounting, Business and Finance Journal*, 8(3), 23-44.
- Apochi, J. G., Mohammed, S. G., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Ownership structure, board of directors and financial performance: Evidence in Nigeria. *Global Review of Accounting and Finance*, 13(1), 77-98.
- Apochi, J. G., Mohammed, S. G., Onyabe, J. M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does corporate governance improve financial performance? Empirical evidence from Africa listed consumer retailing companies. *Management Studies*, 12(1), 111-124.
- Arah, A. B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The impact of SDGs on the socio-economic lives of people of Niger State. *Michigan Journal of Sustainability*, 12(1), 142-178.
- Awen, B. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Can the CEO reverse the increasing leverage of listed firms in Nigeria? *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science*, 12(1), 423-433.
- Awen, B. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Determinants of environmental disclosure quality using Probit estimation among deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Warfare, Command and Capacity Building in Nigeria*. Archers.
- Awen, B. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Gender and nationality among board members and audit quality in Nigerian Listed Firms. *Audit and Accounting Review*, 3(1), 40-57.
- Awen, B. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). The role of women in sustainability reporting. *Wayamba Journal of Management*, 14(1), 16-34.
- Awen, B. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Building a corporate governance index for an emerging market ESG performance. *University of Auckland Business Review*, 27(2), 81-117.
- Awen, B. I., Adewinmisi, G. O., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). The influence of ownership structure on dividend policy in reducing agency problems in Nigeria listed non-financial services companies. *Int Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 12(3), 99-111.
- Awen, B. I., Lamido, A. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Board size, independence and dividend policy in Nigeria. *Intl Journal of Economics and Finance*, 15(5), 72-91.
- Awen, B. I., Onyabe, J. M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Can the board of directors increase firm value? Evidence from the Nigerian Exchange Group. *Korean Accounting Review*, 47(12), 82-97.
- Baba, A. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). The powers of audit and risk committees in constraining earnings management. *Accounting Education*, 32(4), 1-17.
- Charles, Y., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The value relevance of intellectual capital. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 25(2), 233-254.
- Chen, S., & Komal, B. (2018). Audit committee financial expertise and earnings quality: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Business Research*, 84, 253-270.
- Chuma, N., Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The influence of gender diversity on earnings management. *Asian American Research Journal*, 4(2024), 1-30.
- Dimitropoulos, P. E., & Asteriou, D. (2010). The effect of board composition on the informativeness and quality of annual earnings: Empirical evidence from Greece. *Research in International Business and Finance*, 24(2), 190-205.
- Efenyumi, P. M. E. (2022). Risk management committee characteristics' effects on listed companies' earnings quality. *The Journal of Accounting and Management*, 12(3).
- Elhaj, E., Mansor, N., & Salleh, S. I. M. (2022). The effectiveness of risk management committee attributes and real earnings management: Empirical evidence from Malaysia. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 10570-10585.

- Fodio, M. I., Ibikunle, J., & Oba, V. C. (2013). Corporate governance mechanisms and reported earnings quality in listed Nigerian insurance firms. *International Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 2(5), 279-286.
- Garba, M., Yahaya, O. A., & Ahmed, M. N. (2023). Firms characteristics and tax avoidance of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria moderated by board gender. *Journal of Business Studies Quarterly*, 13(1), 1-20.
- Gimbason, J. T., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Ownership structure and sustainability reporting. *Journal of Entrepreneurship and Sustainability Issues*, 12(1), 77-102.
- Hadi, S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Auditors' characteristics and accounting information asymmetry. *Asian Journal of Management Studies*, 3(3), 42-56.
- Hall, A. R. (2003). Generalized method of moments. *A companion to theoretical econometrics*, 230-255.
- Hashim, H. A., & Devi, S. (2008). Board characteristics, ownership structure and earnings quality: Malaysian evidence. In *Corporate governance in less developed and emerging economies* (pp. 97-123). Emerald Group Publishing Limited.
- He, L., Labelle, R., Piot, C., & Thornton, D. B. (2009). Board monitoring, audit committee effectiveness, and financial reporting quality: Review and synthesis of empirical evidence. *Journal of Forensic & Investigative Accounting*, 1(2).
- Hoang, T. C., Abeysekera, I., & Ma, S. (2017). The effect of board diversity on earnings quality: An empirical study of listed firms in Vietnam. *Australian Accounting Review*, 27(2), 146-163.
- Ibrahim, A., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Board demographic characteristics and cost of capital decisions. *Journal of Contemporary Accounting*, 5(2), 126-143.
- Ibrahim, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Ownership structure and leverage. *The Australasian Accounting, Business and Finance Journal*, 17(4), 239-258.
- Ibrahim, S. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Which nomination committee attributes matter in improving financial performance? *Journal of Business Management and Economic Research*, 7(9), 231-257.
- Ibrahim, S. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). An inquiry into the nexus between a CEO and working capital management quality. *J of Smart Economic Growth*, 9(1), 135-163.
- Ibrahim, S. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Applying GMM technique to auditor and value relationship. *Economic and Business*, 37, 247-274.
- Ibrahim, S. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Board of directors and financial statements fraud. *European Journal of Accounting, Finance and Business*, 12(1), 137-167.
- Imbens, G. W. (2002). Generalized method of moments and empirical likelihood. *Journal of Business & Economic Statistics*, 20(4), 493-506.
- Itopa, E., Alexander, S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Board of directors and earnings management: Evidence from the Nigerian Exchange Group. *Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 22(3), 45-59.
- Itopa, E., Imam, M., Musa, U., & Yahaya, O. A. (2019). Corporate governance and capital structure: Evidence from Nigeria listed financial services firms. *Journal of Business Management and Economic Research* (2602-3385), 3(12), 75-89.
- Kabir, Y. I., Tnushi, P. S., Jada, R., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Ownership demographics and financial performance of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria moderated by firm size. *Journal of Accounting and Management*, 13(3), 141-162.
- Katmon, N., & Farooque, O. A. (2017). Exploring the impact of internal corporate governance on the relation between disclosure quality and earnings management in the UK listed companies. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 142, 345-367.
- Kent, P., Kent, R. A., Routledge, J., & Stewart, J. (2016). Choice of governance structure and earnings quality. *Accounting Research Journal*, 29(4), 372-390.

- Khalil, M., & Ozkan, A. (2016). Board independence, audit quality and earnings management: Evidence from Egypt. *Journal of Emerging Market Finance*, 15(1), 84-118.
- Kontesa, M., Lako, A., & Wendy, W. (2020). Board ownership and earnings quality with different controlling shareholders. *Accounting Research Journal*, 33(4/5), 593-613.
- Lamido, I. A., Ibrahim, M. F., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Audit committee and financial performance: Evidence from Nigeria. *Review of Applied Management and Social Sciences*, 6(1), 581-590.
- Lamido, I. A., Yusuf, M. J., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). A meta-analysis of female directors and instability in firm value in Nigeria. *China Journal of Accounting Studies*, 11(7), 325-337.
- Lawal, R., Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The impact of corporate governance on integrated reporting. *Management Decision*, 62(1), 370-392.
- Lin, J. W., Li, J. F., & Yang, J. S. (2006). The effect of audit committee performance on earnings quality. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 21(9), 921-933.
- Muhammad, Z., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The value relevance of ESG performance disclosure. *Journal of Sustainability Science and Management*, 19(4), 123-140.
- Murtala, S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). The effects of risk committee characteristics on bank asset quality. *Asian-Pacific Journal of Mgt and Technology*, 4(1), 35-51.
- Musa, Z., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Corporate governance and firm value. *Budapest International Research and Critics Institute Journal (Humanities and Social Sciences)*, 6(4), 204-220.
- Ogaki, M. (1993). 17 Generalized method of moments: Econometric applications.
- Okaro, S. C., & Okafor, G. O. (2013). Drivers of audit failure in Nigeria: Evidence from Cadbury (Nigeria) PLC. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 4(6), 1686-1697.
- Okodo, B. D., Aliu, M. M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2019). Assessing the reliability of the internal audit functions: The issues. *Journal of Contemporary Research in Business, Economics and Finance*, 1(1), 46-55.
- Olagunji, A. S., Yahaya, O. A., & Ahmed, M. N. (2023). Board attributes and integrated reporting of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. *AFRE Accounting and Financial Review*, 6(1), 331-362.
- Onyabe, J. M., Tijjani, B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). CEO and integrated reporting: Evidence from Africa listed communication services companies. *Afro-Asian Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 13(2), 86-99.
- Otuya, S., Donwa, P., & Egware, N. (2017). Earnings management and quality of corporate governance in Nigeria: A review of executive compensation and audit committee characteristics. *Journal of Accounting and Financial Management*, 3(3), 2017.
- Ozoelo, J. I., Yahaya, O. A., & Joshua, S. G. (2023). Audit committee and audit delay of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. *Indonesian Accounting Literacy Journal*, 3(4), 226-242.
- Pratiwi, W., & Pralita, T. (2021). The influence of corporate governance mechanism, accounting conservatism, and company size on earnings quality. *Journal of Economics, Finance and Management Studies*, 4(01), 26-34.
- Puat Nelson, S., & Devi, S. (2013). Audit committee experts and earnings quality. *Corporate Governance: The international journal of business in society*, 13(4), 335-351.
- Salisu, Y., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The influence of female CEO on company leverage. *Journal of Economics and Business*, 34, 81-107.
- Samaila, N., Suleiman, R., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Corporate boards and leverage decisions. *Accounting Forum*, 47(2), 307-326
- Shuaibu, K., Abdulwahab, A. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Corporate governance and dividend policy. *Economics and Business Quarterly*, 6(3), 125-141.

- Sierra García, L., Ruiz Barbadillo, E., & Orta Pérez, M. (2012). Audit committee and internal audit and the quality of earnings: empirical evidence from Spanish companies. *Journal of Management & Governance*, 16, 305-331.
- Sulaiman, L., Abdulwahab, A. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Board of directors and auditor choice. *South Asian Journal of Finance*, 3(1), 38-59.
- Suleiman, U., Popoola, A., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Equity financing and financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research in Innovation and Social Science*, 6(12), 618-624.
- Susilo, J. H., Tsani, L. I., Herianto, H., & Kholilurrohman, M. (2020). Econometrics Model of Economic Growth in East Java Province with Dynamic Panel Data through Generalized Method of Moment (GMM) Approach. *Ekulilibrium: Jurnal Ilmiah Bidang Ilmu Ekonomi*, 15(1), 38-54.
- Sutradhar, B. C., Rao, R. P., & Pandit, V. N. (2008). Generalized method of moments versus generalized quasi-likelihood inferences in binary panel data models. *Sankhyā: The Indian Journal of Statistics, Series B (2008-)*, 34-62.
- Syofya, H. (2022). Modeling Analysis of Economic Growth in Asia with a Dynamic Panel Approach Generalized Method of Moment (GMM). *IJEED (International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Business Development)*, 5(4), 716-725.
- Teritlak, M. (2016). Determinants of innovation in developing countries: A panel generalized method of moments analysis. *Jurnal Ekonomi Malaysia*, 50(2), 93-105.
- Tijjani, B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does corporate governance improve energy information disclosure among Nigeria listed manufacturing firms? *Journal of Advanced Research in Business and Management Studies*, 26(3), 15-26.
- Tijjani, B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). A bibliometric analysis of corporate ownership demographics and sustainability reporting quality in Nigeria. *International Journal of Managerial and Financial Accounting*, 15(3), 393-410.
- Tijjani, B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). The impact of CEO female gender diversity and nationality on Internal Control System Disclosure: Empirical Evidence from Nigeria. *Int Research Journal of Management, IT and Social Sciences*, 10(2), 50-61.
- Tijjani, B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). CEO characteristics and corporate risk taking. *International Journal of Corporate Governance*, 14(1), 94-116.
- Ullah, S., Akhtar, P., & Zaefarian, G. (2018). Dealing with endogeneity bias: The generalized method of moments (GMM) for panel data. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 71, 69-78.
- Umar, M. M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Board of directors and bankruptcy risk using GMM approach. *Applied Finance and Accounting*, 9(1), 242-256.
- Usman, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Board Committees' Independence and Intellectual Capital Efficiency in Corporate Nigeria. *The Journal of Bus.*, 8(1), 36-47.
- Usman, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Do corporate governance mechanisms improve earnings? *China Journal of Accounting Research*, 16, 1-13.
- Usman, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). The dynamics between a CEO and risk disclosure in Nigeria. *Accounting and Auditing Review*, 30(1), 1-13.
- Usman, S. O., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Corporate governance and credit ratings in Nigeria. *Int Journal of Economics, Management and Finance*, 2(1), 62-71.
- Usman, S. O., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Effect of board characteristics on firm value in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Finance*, 47(1), 44-60.
- Usman, S. O., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). The CEO power and sustainability reporting of listed firms in Nigeria. *J. of Business Mgt. and Accounting*, 13(7), 106-125.
- Wan Ismail, W. A. B. (2011). *Earnings quality, family influence and corporate governance: Empirical evidence from Malaysia* (Doctoral dissertation, Open Access Te Herenga Waka-Victoria University of Wellington).

- Warsono, W., Utami, B. H., Kurniasari, D., & Usman, M. (2014). Generalized method of moments' characteristics and its application on panel data. *Science International*, 26(3), 985-990.
- Weber, L. (2020). Is audit committee expertise related to earnings quality? Evidence from Germany. *Journal of Managerial Issues*, 32(3).
- Wild, J. J. (1996). The audit committee and earnings quality. *Journal of Accounting, Auditing & Finance*, 11(2), 247-276.
- Wooldridge, J. M. (2001). Applications of generalized method of moments estimation. *Journal of Economic perspectives*, 15(4), 87-100.
- Yahaya, O. A. & Lamidi, Y. S. (2015). Empirical examination of the financial performance of Islamic bank in Nigeria. *International Journal of Accounting Research*, 2(7), 1-13.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2006). Empirical evidence on the effect of size on the profitability of commercial banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Social Studies*, 11(4), 33-39.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2014). Social disclosure and financial performance: Evidence from Nigeria listed firms. *Nigerian Journal of Accounting Research*, 10(2), 47-66.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2017). Firm performance and dividend policy: A panel data analysis of listed consumer-goods companies in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Management Technology and Development*, 8(1), 306-322.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2018). Environmental reporting practices and financial performance of listed environmentally-sensitive firms in Nigeria. *Savanna: A Journal of the Environmental and Social Sciences*, 24(2), 403-412.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2019). Intellectual capital management and financial competitiveness of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. *Enugu State University of Technology Journal of Management Sciences*, 12(1&2), 86-96.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2021). Analysts' forecasts and stock prices: Evidence from Nigeria. *Iranian Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance*, 5(2), 01-10.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Can the CEO improve intellectual capital? *International Journal of Finance, Accounting and Economics Studies*, 3(1), 84-100.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Chief executive officer and firm value: Evidence from Nigeria listed non-financial services companies. *J of Econ & Financial Studies*, 10(3), 12-21.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Corporate governance and profitability: An Application of Agency Theory. *Journal of Accounting Research*, 34(2), 406-421.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does Board Gender Diversity Influence Dividend Pay-Out? Evidence from Nigeria Non-Financial Services Sector. *International J. of Accounting, Finance and Risk Management*, 7(2), 25-33.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does CEO characteristics affect dividend policy? *Review of Accounting Studies*, 27(2), 375-389.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does CEOs influence earnings management? *South African Journal of Accounting Research*, 36(2), 1-13.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Electronic payments system and economic growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Management and Economics*, 5(20), 45-54.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Female directors and financial performance. Does audit committee play a role? *Advances in Accounting*, 58(C), 248-258.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Abdulfatah, L. A. (2022). Can auditors reduce earnings management activities? *Review of Accounting and Finance (ISSN: 1475-7702)*, 22(4), 429-442.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Alexander, A. A. (2015). Business process management and financial performance: An exploratory study of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Accounting Frontier*, 17(1), 43-75.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Alkasim A. (2021). Sustainability and profitability of listed insurance firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Accounting and Finance*,

6(1), 17-28.

Yahaya, O. A., & Andow, H. A. (2015). Capital structure and firm's financial performance: Panel evidence of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria. *Kaduna Business Management Review*, 2(1), 1-25.

Yahaya, O. A., & Apochi, J. (2021). Board of directors and corporate social responsibility reporting of quoted companies in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting, Finance and Auditing Studies*, 7(2), 38-52.

Yahaya, O. A., & Apochi, J. G. (2022). The board of directors' influence on the intellectual capital of Nigeria listed firms. *Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance*, 37(2), 1-17.

Yahaya, O. A., & Awen, B. I. (2020). Bank-specific attributes and operational efficiency: Evidence from Efficient-Structure Hypothesis. *Journal of Business and Social Review in Emerging Economies*, 6(3), 1087-1098.

Yahaya, O. A., & Awen, B. I. (2021). Chief executive officers and bankruptcy of quoted resources companies in Nigeria. *Fountain Journal of Mgt Sciences*, 10(2), 970-980.

Yahaya, O. A., & Awen, B. I. (2022). Does ownership structure lead to optimal financial structure? *Seisense Journal of Management*, 5(4), 51-64.

Yahaya, O. A., & Lamido, I. A. (2022). Corporate social responsibility and financial performance. Evidence from Nigeria. *International Journal of Accounting and Finance Review*, 10(1), 107-120.

Yahaya, O. A., & Mohammed, S. G. (2022). Does board of directors improve profitability? *Accounting*, 8, 269-275.

Yahaya, O. A., & Ogwiji, J. (2021). Risk committee traits and profitability of Nigerian banking sector. *Accounting, Finance & Management: Texts and Applications*, 01-14.

Yahaya, O. A., & Onyabe, J. M. (2020). Firm life cycle and financial performance: Evidence from Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting and Finance in Emerging Economies*, 6(3), 723-732.

Yahaya, O. A., & Onyabe, J. M. (2022). Audit committee and integrated reporting. *European Research Studies Journal*, 25(4), 305-318.

Yahaya, O. A., & Onyabe, J. M. (2022). Do audit fees and auditor independence affect audit quality? *Asian Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 14(1), 66-80.

Yahaya, O. A., & Onyabe, J. M. (2022). The nexus between audit committee and audit fees. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 53(6), 966-984.

Yahaya, O. A., & Tijani, B. (2020). Internal corporate governance and intellectual capital of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. *European J. of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 8(9), 98-112.

Yahaya, O. A., & Tijjani, B. (2021). Size, age and leverage of Nigeria quoted oil and gas corporations. *Advanced International Journal of Banking, Accounting and Finance*, 3(6), 51-60.

Yahaya, O. A., & Yakubu, I. (2022). Risk committee's influence on enterprise risk management. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 15(4): 120, 1-15.

Yahaya, O. A., & Yusuf, M. J. (2020). Ethical behavioural disclosure and financial performance of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. *Sustainable Business and Society in Emerging Economies*, 2(2), 13-20.

Yahaya, O. A., Farouk, B. K. U., Lamidi, S. Y., Yusuf, M. J., & Dania, I. S. (2015). Impact of competition on the financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 6(18), 52-61.

Yahaya, O. A., Kutigi, U. M., & Ahmed, M. (2014). Country-specific characteristics as determinants of financial performance: Evidence from listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting*, 3(2), 77-101.

Yahaya, O. A., Kutigi, U. M., & Ahmed, M. (2015). International financial reporting

- standards and earnings management behavior of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *European Journal of Business Management*, 7(18), 70-82.
- Yahaya, O. A., Kutigi, U. M., Solanke, A. A., Onyabe, J. M. & Usman, S. O. (2015). Current assets management and financial performance: Evidence from listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Int Journal of African and Asian Studies*, 13, 45-56.
- Yahaya, O. A., Lamidi, Y. S., Kutigi, U. M., & Ahmed, M. (2015). The correlation between risk management and organizational performance: an empirical investigation using panel data. *Res J. of Finance and Accounting*, 6(16), 136-146.
- Yahaya, O. A., Mohammed, I., & Mohammed, S. G. (2022). Board governance and sustainability disclosure of Nigeria Listed Deposit Money Banks. *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 10(5), 126-146.
- Yahaya, O. A., Onyabe, J. M., & Usman, S. O. (2015). Determinants of productivity of listed deposit money banks: An empirical estimation using panel data. *Journal of Accounting*, 4(1), 79-93.
- Yahaya, O. A., Onyabe, J. M., & Usman, S. O. (2015). International financial reporting standards and value relevance of accounting information of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Dev.*, 6(12), 85-93.
- Yahaya, O. A., Onyabe, J. M., Yusuf, M. J., & Bilyaminu, T. (2019). Financial mix and financial performance of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting and Management*, 2(1), 226-237.
- Yahaya, O. A., Tanko, M., & Muhammad, L. M. (2017). Effects of corporate characteristics on earnings quality of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Management Sciences*, 8(1), 47-64.
- Yahaya, O. A., Yusuf, M. J., & Dania, I. S. (2015). International financial reporting standards' adoption and financial statement effects: Evidence from listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Research J. of Finance and Accounting*, 6(12), 107-122.
- Yakubu, S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Auditors' characteristics and variability in integrated reporting gravity. *International Journal of Accounting, Finance and Business*, 8(50), 234-255.
- Yusuf, M. J., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). CEO attributes and financial performance of listed firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics, Finance and Management Sciences*, 11(2), 112-124.
- Zgarni, I., Hlioui, K., & Zehri, F. (2016). Effective audit committee, audit quality and earnings management: Evidence from Tunisia. *Journal of Accounting in Emerging Economies*, 6(2), 138-155.

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